

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Том 2, Выпуск 2, 29 Февраль

REHABILITATION MEASURES IN DISEASES OF THE MUSCULOSKELETAL SYSTEM

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Abstract. This article talks about the basic human movement system and rehabilitative measures for its diseases.

Key words. Musculoskeletal system, skeleton, muscles, body, bones, tendons, body, heart, lungs.

The main part. The musculoskeletal system of a person is understood as a complex consisting of skeleton and skeletal muscles. First of all, this system is the support of the whole organism and a protective shell surrounding the internal organs (heart, lungs, stomach, kidneys, spleen, etc.). Movement is the way of life of every living organism. It is this musculoskeletal system that makes it happen. All vital processes in the body are kept in order only when there is constant movement.

This is the system consists of 3 parts:

1. Bone
2. Muscle
3. Pay

Children with various congenital and early acquired diseases and injuries of the musculoskeletal system have similar characteristics, and most complaints are focused on movement disorders. (violations of body formation, lagging behind in development, limited movement in some parts of the body, etc.)

Some children with this pathology do not have mental deviations and do not require special educational measures. But all children with musculoskeletal disorders need special living conditions, education and specialized work conditions.

"When a part of the human body moves, first of all, we need to consider the joints in which the movement is taking place, the position of the joints, and how the muscles

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work."¹ In order for the human body to be kept in balance, the vertical line from the center of gravity must pass through the plane of support of the body. Only then can the body be kept in a vertical position. Improper holding of the body or some parts of the body in a disproportionate and asymmetrical way indicates the presence of muscle pathology. In this way, we should assume that the muscle structure changes as a result of the underdevelopment of the muscles (congenital defect) or an injury. A severe burn, a strong deep wound, or an acutely active chemical destroys the integrity of the muscle structure. Over a period of time, the muscle tissue regenerates (restores) itself, but in the process of healing, connective scar tissue is formed in the damaged muscle part. This tissue is not elastic and stretchable. As a result, the muscle is overgrown, but its structure, movement, and activity have changed. This condition is called contracture.

Causes of musculoskeletal disorders:

1. Pathologies of the fetus (currently it has been proven that more than 400 factors can affect the central nervous system of the developing fetus, they have a particularly dangerous effect until the 4th month of the fetus):

- infectious diseases of the mother, consequences of somatic diseases of the mother, severe toxicosis;

- Rhesus factor or blood group incompatibility;

- Injuries to the fetus,

- intoxication;

- environmental hazards.

2. Birth injuries, asphyxia.

3. Pathological factors affecting the child's body in the first year of life: neuroinfections (meningitis, encephalitis, etc.); injuries to the child's head, complications after vaccination.

There are many factors that have a negative effect on movement, that is, on the human body and specifically on the organs of movement (muscles, bones, tendons and joints):

- inflammation of muscle tissue (myositis);

- inflammation of bone tissue (osteitis, osteomyelitis);

- joint inflammation (arthritis).

¹ Ulxoj'jayeva K.E., Xudoyberganova B.T. Fizioterapiya va tibbiy reabilitatsiya.T., 2004.

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"Arthritis is a symptom of many infectious and allergic diseases, and it does a lot of harm to a person."² In particular, in rheumatism, inflammation of the connective tissue present in the joints is observed. This disease is caused by β -hemolytic streptococcus. So, we consider a bacterial or viral infection as a factor that causes limitation of movement

Children with mild musculoskeletal disorders.

Correct posture is not only aesthetic, but also physiologically important - it contributes to the normal functioning of internal organs, as deviations in the position affect their functions. So that the child does not have problems with increased fatigue, headaches and pain in the muscles of the body at school, it is necessary to start as soon as possible to prevent musculoskeletal disorders or to correct the existing condition.

Feet are the foundation and support of our body, and any developmental disorder affects the child's health. At preschool age, the legs are in the stage of intensive development, and its formation is not yet complete, so any negative external influences can lead to the appearance of certain functional abnormalities. Congenital flat feet is rare. It often develops in weakened, physically underdeveloped children with rickets.

The main types of diseases of the musculoskeletal system in children of preschool age:

Hip dysplasia, valgus deformity of knee joints, acquired and congenital flat feet, scoliotic stature, kyphotic stature, chest deformity.

Children with various disorders of the locomotor system and insufficient sensorimotor development experience certain difficulties in learning the curriculum. These defects are often associated with insufficient development of thinking, perception, attention, memory, and the lack of formation of all components of the speech system.

"In children with dysfunction of the musculoskeletal system, mental activity decreases, fatigue increases, which makes the formation of mental activity difficult and leads to its disruption."³

In preschool children, articular movements slow down, dynamic coordination, and the balance of fine and general movements are disturbed.

Injury is another serious factor that causes limitation of movement. There are many types of injuries, including cuts (under the influence of a cutting object), lacerations, punctures or lacerations, lacerations. There are also injuries such as stretching and

² Содиков Б.А., Кучкарова Л.С., Курбанов Ш.К. Болалар ва ўсмирлар физиологияси ва гигиенаси. Тошкент, "Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси" - 2005.

³ F.Sh.Bahodirova. Reabilitatsiya, massaj va mehnat bn davolash.Toshkent «IQTISOD-MOLIYA» 20162.

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breaking of tendons, dislocation of joints, and broken bones, which are the direct cause of limitation or impairment of movement.

Muscle-movement depends on impulses arriving through nerve fibers. That is, under the influence of a nerve impulse, this or that muscle moves and contracts and performs its task. If the patient has a central or peripheral nerve disease, this affects the movement disorder. For example, if the nerve fibers between the spine are damaged in the neck, not only the hands, but also the legs and organs of the small pelvis can be damaged. Inflammation of the facial nerve causes a change in the structure of the face (asymmetry), and as a result, the activity of the muscles of the inflamed side is disturbed, that is, the process of swallowing and chewing becomes difficult. Movement disorders and limitations in children's diseases. It is also common in children. But the main factor that causes immobility of children is rickets. This disease is common in children under one year of age. In rickets, as a result of vitamin D deficiency, calcium (Ca) content in the child's body decreases, calcium metabolism is disturbed. This has a negative effect. Due to the poor absorption of calcium in the body, the child experiences hair loss, strong sweating, moodiness, muscle twitching, hypotrophy (wasting), retardation of development and osteomalacia (bone softening), osteodeformation (bone bending). Children also have MAT diseases, which cause movement disorders. Including children with cerebral palsy, plexitis, and birth injuries.

The musculoskeletal system consists of the skeleton and muscles, which are the support of the body and the protective shell surrounding the internal organs, and participate in the processes of support, movement, blood formation. Bones are passive in movement, and muscles are actively involved. If the growth of the skeleton ends at the age of 20-25, the growth and development of the muscles can be up to the age of 30-35. The correct formation of the musculoskeletal system has a great impact on the development of all internal organs and the nervous system.

Musculoskeletal system includes the implementation of medical exercises and surgery designed to treat these diseases. Rehabilitators can help you improve your healing ability through a personalized treatment regimen and targeted exercises. Physical therapy, therapy, and massage are part of the rehabilitation program, so that the musculoskeletal system can be treated with good results.

There are two main types of medical rehabilitation: general rehabilitation and private rehabilitation. General rehabilitation refers to the strengthening and restoration of human health with the help of procedures that affect the overall functioning of the human body, general condition and all systems. In order to restore the functioning of diseased organs in the patient's body, special treatments are widely used along with natural factors.

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Functional rehabilitation means a set of procedures and factors used to restore the function of a body part whose activity is limited or impaired due to complications of an illness or injury. In addition to medical rehabilitation, there are several types of rehabilitation: mental rehabilitation, social rehabilitation, etc. Medical social worker has a great role in medical rehabilitation. This field requires a high level of knowledge, patience, love for the patient, empathy and responsibility.

Conclusion: Musculoskeletal disorders are areas of knowledge that can be developed during other experiences in orthopedic medicine or post-surgical trauma. In these diseases, rehabilitology fulfills its tasks by providing measures and measures.

In diseases of the locomotor system, rehabilitation measures allow to improve the mobility of the patient and improve his quality of life. These interventions may include physical therapy, massage, music and art therapy, psychological support, excessive exercise, and other methods. The rehabilitation process is formed based on the characteristics and needs of the monitored patient. These activities support the bowls and allow them to participate in various activities.

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